

In-network reconstruction of jointly sparse signals with ADMM

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Abstract—In this paper, we tackle the problem of in-network recovery of sparse signals. We assume that the nodes of the network measure a signal composed by a common component and an innovation, both sparse and unknown, according to the Joint Sparsity Model 1 (JSM-1). We present a distributed algorithm based on the alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM) to recover such signals, along with a second version requiring only binary messaging. Then we assess the impact of the compression level at the acquisition stage and measurement noise on such schemes.

I. INTRODUCTION AND SIGNAL MODEL

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the use of the so-called Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM, [1, Chapter 2]) for distributed problems with sparsity constraints. In the framework of in-network reconstruction, the development of distributed versions of ADMM has been addressed e.g., in [2], [3]. For general multi-agent problems, a distributed ADMM scheme has been proposed in [4], which is proved to converge and exhibit a faster convergence rate than state-of-the-art subgradient methods. In such works, each node i in the network is associated with a local variable x_i and a function f_i , such that the functional f to be minimized is separable and given by $f(x) = \sum_i f_i(x_i)$, where $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots)^T$. Those variables are coupled by a set of linear constraints which impose (local) consensus. This papers, however, addresses a more general model: the joint sparsity model 1 (JSM-1, [5]), according to which the signal to be recovered at each node is given by the sum of a component common to all the network nodes plus an individual innovation component, both sparse and unknown. Interestingly, the two variables can be updated sequentially, in such a way so that all the nodes can proceed in parallel, in contrast to [2], [4]. To that aim, we propose a distributed version of the aforementioned ADMM, along with a second version in which only binary messaging is required. Then, we assess the impact of the compression level at the acquisition stage and measurement noise on such schemes.

Consider a network composed of N nodes whose connectivity is described through the connected graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{E})$ where \mathcal{N} and \mathcal{E} stand for the set of vertices and edges. Node $i \in \mathcal{N}$ can communicate with node $j \in \mathcal{N}$ if j belongs to the neighborhood set of i , denoted as \mathcal{N}_i . Each node observes a

compressed version of a signal $\{x_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \in \mathbb{R}^L$ through a set of linear and local measurements, namely

$$y_i = A_i x_i + \eta_i \quad ; \quad i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (1)$$

where $A_i \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times L}$ (with $M \ll L$) stands for the measurement matrix at the i -th node and $\eta_i \in \mathbb{R}^M$ for additive noise. We further assume that the observed signals follow the JSM-1 model [5], namely

$$x_i = \Psi z_c + \Phi z_i \quad ; \quad i \in \mathcal{N} \quad (2)$$

where $\Psi, \Phi \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times L}$, and $z_c, z_i \in \mathbb{R}^L$. That is, the observed signal at each node is composed of a common component z_c plus an innovation component z_i which are unknown and sparse in some domains given by the orthogonal bases Ψ and Φ . We define the *support* of z_c or z_i as the (indexed and possibly different) subset of non-zero components in those vectors, of cardinality k_c and k_i , respectively. Hereinafter, and without loss of generality, we assume $\Psi = \Phi = I_L$. The ultimate goal is to reconstruct the triplets $\{x_i, z_c, z_i\}$ at each node in a distributed manner. To that end, we attempt to solve the following convex optimization problem:

$$\min_{\{x_i, z_i, z_c\}} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\|y_i - A_i x_i\|_2^2 + \tau_1 \|z_i\|_1 + \tau_2 \|z_c\|_1 \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad x_i = z_c + z_i; \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (4)$$

with $\tau_1, \tau_2 > 0$ denoting weights aimed to promote sparsity in the individual and common components, respectively.

II. DISTRIBUTED ADMM (DADMM) FOR JSM-1

In order to find a *distributed* reconstruction method, we propose to solve the following optimization problem (for details on its centralized counterpart, see [6]):

$$\min_{\{x_i, z_i, \zeta_i, c_i\}} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i - A_i x_i\|_2^2 + \tau_1 \|z_i\|_1 + \tau_2 \|\zeta_i\|_1 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad x_i = z_i + \zeta_i; \quad i \in \mathcal{N} \quad (6)$$

$$\zeta_i = c_j; \quad j \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_i \quad (7)$$

with $\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_i = \mathcal{N}_i \cup i$. Here, we have introduced the local variables $\{\zeta_i\}, \{c_i\}$ that must be interpreted as the local and neighbors' guesses on the common component z_i in (4). The consensus constraint of (7) and the fact that \mathcal{G} is a connected graph render the problem above still equivalent to (3)-(7). In order to solve

(5)–(7), we resort to the ADMM scheme. To that aim, we build the corresponding augmented Lagrangian:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(x, z, \zeta; \lambda, \mu) = & \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \left\{ \|y_i - A_i x_i\|_2^2 + \tau_1 \|z_i\|_1 + \tau_2 \|\zeta_i\|_1 \right. \\ & + \frac{\rho}{2} \|x_i - z_i - \zeta_i\|_2^2 + \frac{\theta}{2} \sum_{j \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_i} \|\zeta_i - c_j\|_2^2 \\ & \left. + \lambda_i^T (x_i - z_i - \zeta_i) + \sum_{j \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_i} \mu_{i,j}^T (\zeta_i - c_j) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

with ρ and θ standing for positive constants, and $\{\lambda_i\}$, $\{\mu_{i,j}\}$ denoting the the Lagrangian multipliers associated with constraints (6), (7), respectively. This augmented Lagrangian function is needed for the update of the primal and dual variables. Specifically, we propose to sequentially update the primal variables $\{x_i, z_i, \zeta_i, c_i\}$ according to

$$x_i(t+1) = (\rho I_L + A_i^T A_i)^{-1} (A_i^T y_i + \rho(z_i(t) + \zeta_i(t)) - \lambda_i^T)$$

$$z_i(t+1) = \mathcal{S}_{\frac{\tau_1}{\rho}} \left[(x_i(t+1) - \zeta_i(t)) + \frac{\lambda_i(t)}{\rho} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_i(t+1) = & \mathcal{S}_{\frac{\tau_2}{\rho + \theta |\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_i|}} \left[\frac{1}{\rho + \theta |\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_i|} (\rho (x_i(t+1) - z_i(t+1)) \right. \\ & \left. + \theta \sum_{j \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_i} \left(c_j(t) - \frac{\mu_{i,j}(t)}{\theta} \right) + \lambda_i(t) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$c_i(t+1) = \frac{1}{|\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_i|} \sum_{j:i \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_j} \left(\zeta_j(t+1) + \frac{\mu_{j,i}(t)}{\theta} \right); \quad (9)$$

followed by the ascent updates of the dual variables, that is,

$$\lambda_i(t+1) = \lambda_i(t) + \alpha (x_i(t+1) - z_i(t+1) - \zeta_i(t+1))$$

$$\mu_{i,j}(t+1) = \mu_{i,j}(t) + \kappa (\zeta_i(t+1) - c_j(t+1)); \quad j \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_i,$$

where α and κ are positive constants; and $\mathcal{S}_\alpha : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ with $\alpha > 0$ stands for the component-wise soft-thresholding operator as defined in [6]. Interestingly, this iterative method can be readily implemented in a distributed manner by just exchanging information ($\{\zeta_i, c_i\}$) among neighboring nodes. Further, in [6] we also proposed the so-called DADMM-1bit version of the scheme where such information was roughly quantized with 1 bit. This results into savings in terms of signalling and energy consumption (note that $\{\zeta_i, c_i\}$ are large and real-valued vectors). To that aim, though, the primal updates of (8) and (9) must be replaced by gradient updates of constant step ϵ .

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

In the simulations, we consider signals $\{x_i\}$ of length $L = 100$ with sparsity levels $k_i = k_c = 5$. The supports of the common and innovation signals $\{z_c, z_i\}$ are randomly generated with non-zero elements drawn from a standard Gaussian distribution. As performance metric, we adopt the normalized mean square error which for a generic k -sparse signal x and its reconstruction \hat{x} is defined as $\text{MSE}(x) = \frac{1}{k\sigma_x^2} \|\hat{x} - x\|_2^2$.

In Figure 1, we depict the MSE in reconstruction of the common and innovation (individual) components as a function of M , the number of measurements per sensor. For $M = 24$,

Figure 1. MSE attained by DADMM in the reconstruction of $\{z_i\}$, z_c and x_i vs the number of measurements per sensor M ($N = 20$, $k_i = k_c = 5$, $L = 100$, $d = 5$, $\tau_1 = 3e-2$, $\tau_2 = 1e-2$).

Figure 2. MSE in the (distributed) reconstruction of $\{z_i\}$, z_c vs SNR of the measurements ($N = 20$, $k_i = k_c = 5$, $M = 25$, $d = 5$, $L = 100$, $d = 5$, $\tau_1 = 3e-2$, $\tau_2 = 1e-2$, $\rho = \theta = 0.01$, $\epsilon = 0.01$).

the DADMM scheme achieves perfect reconstruction although, as discussed in [6], the number of iterations needed is larger than for its centralized counterpart. In all cases, though, the MSE in the reconstruction of z_c is lower than that of z_i . This stems from the fact that nodes actually collaborate in the estimation of the common component (this still allowing for a perfect reconstruction of z_c for $M = 20$) whereas such collaboration is not possible for the estimation of the innovation component.

Next, Figure 2 illustrates the impact of measurement noise. Interestingly, DADMM is less affected by noisy measurements than its 1-bit counterpart (MSE is higher in both components). This is in stark contrast with the noiseless case discussed in [6] where, for small update steps ($\epsilon = 0,01$), both DADMM and DADMM-1bit schemes exhibited identical reconstruction error (yet the latter required more iterations).

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